

WORKFORCE MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES IN MYANMAR SMES: THE IMPACT OF LABOR MIGRATION AND ECONOMIC CRISIS ON STRATEGIC DECISION-MAKING

Abstract

SMEs play a crucial role in national economy development by creating employment opportunities and poverty reduction, although they face challenges to operate their operations within limited resources. After the pandemic crisis (COVID-19 pandemic) and 2021 political instabilities, SMEs in Myanmar have encountered increasing difficulties in retaining a stable, skilled, and productive workforce. Labor migration, driven by safety concerns, political conditions, and economic uncertainty, has intensified workforce shortage, increased competition for talent, and weakened business competitiveness. However, there is critical gap of scientific evidence how the effect of labor migration and economic crisis impact on workforce management challenges and the development of strategic decision-making among SMEs in Myanmar. The current study adopts a quantitative approach and integrates decision-making framework such as the Cynefin framework, the OODA loop, and the PCDA cycle to analyze how SMEs respond to uncertainty. Primary data are collected through self-administered questionnaire from 126 SME owners, managers, and senior staff. The data are analyzed using SPSS (version 27), employing One-way ANOVA, and linear regression. The findings showed that labor migration has a significant negative impact on workforce management, leading to shortages of skilled labor, increased recruitment difficulties, higher wage expectations, and reduced productivity. Moreover, the economic crisis increases operational costs, employee financial stress, and limits investment in workforce development. The results indicate regional differences in how SMEs experience these challenges. Both labor migration and economic instability are found to significantly influence strategic decision-making. SMEs adopt various coping strategies, including offering competitive wages, training employees, hiring temporary staff, and utilizing automation. The study recommends Kotter's 8-step change model to support long-term organizational resilience and systematic workforce management improvement.

Keywords: Workforce Management, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), Labor Migration, Economic Crisis, Strategic Decision-Making, Human Resource Challenges, Organizational Adaptation, Change Management, Myanmar.

I. Problem Identification

Employees are a fundamental driver of organizational success and productivity, as they perform essential tasks to produce goods, deliver services, and achieve business objectives. Human resource (HR) management plays a critical role in managing employees through activities such as recruitment, training, and workplace practices (Anggraini et al., 2024). Workforce management, as an extension of HR, focuses on ensuring that the right number of employees with appropriate skills are available at the right time (Sitompul & Dewi, 2023). It is particularly important for small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which rely on limited human resources to conduct daily operations (Harney & Nolan, 2022). Effective workforce management enables SMEs to allocate tasks efficiently, and improve productivity. Managing employees in SMEs is challenging due to limited resources and managerial capacity (Haist & Novotný, 2023). Economic crises create financial instability, reduce demand, and increase operational costs, making it difficult for businesses to sustain effective workforce strategies.

In Myanmar, SMEs are the backbone of economy, accounting for approximately 94% of registered enterprises and employing a significant proportion of the labor force. They play a vital role in job

creation, poverty reduction, and economic development across sectors such as manufacturing, agriculture, retail, and services (Ministry of Information, 2024). However, SMEs face multiple challenges, including limited access to finance, market constraints, and economic instability. Since 2020, exchange rate volatility, inflation, and political instability have further intensified these challenges. Labor migration has become a significant issue in Myanmar, particularly following the 2021 political crisis. Both internal and international migration have increased as workers seek better opportunities and security. Businesses shift from growth-oriented approaches to survival-oriented strategies, increase wages to retain employees, and invest more in training new hires, thereby raising operational costs. SMEs face increasing difficulties in making effective strategic decisions. Despite their critical role in the economy, there is limited research on how labor migration and economic crises influence workforce management and decision-making in Myanmar. Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of these factors on workforce management challenges and strategic decision-making among SMEs in Myanmar.

II. Decision-Making Frameworks

2.1 The Cynefin Framework

The Cynefin Framework, developed by Dave Snowden in 1999, is a decision-making model that helps leaders address complex and uncertain situations (Gupta, 2025). The term *Cynefin*, meaning “place of belonging,” reflects how individuals and organizations operate within different contexts. The framework highlights that not all problems are the same and require different decision-making approaches. It consists of five domains: clear, complicated, complex, chaotic, and disorder, each representing different relationships between cause and effect. Clear and complicated domains are ordered contexts where problems are predictable or can be analyzed, while complex and chaotic domains are unordered, with unclear and rapidly changing conditions. The disorder domain occurs when it is uncertain which context applies. By identifying the nature of a situation, leaders can apply appropriate strategies, such as following best practices, consulting experts, experimenting, or taking immediate action. The framework is widely used in modern organizations to support strategic decision-making, innovation, and crisis management. Although it enhances adaptability and resilience, its effectiveness depends on accurate problem classification and proper understanding by decision-makers.

2.2 OODA Loop

The OODA loop (Observe, Orient, Decide, Act), developed by Colonel John Boyd, is a decision-making framework that supports organizations in responding effectively to dynamic and uncertain environments (Richards, 2020). The process begins with the “Observe” stage, where organizations collect relevant data from sources such as operational metrics, market trends, and customer feedback to build situational awareness. The second stage, “Orient,” involves analyzing and interpreting the collected information to generate meaningful insights. This phase helps organizations understand internal performance, customer preferences, and external market conditions. The “Decide” stage follows, where leaders evaluate alternatives and select appropriate strategies based on the analyzed data. This stage is critical for aligning decisions with organizational objectives and responding to emerging challenges. Finally, the “Act” stage involves implementing the chosen strategies through concrete actions such as process improvements, resource allocation, or market responses. The OODA loop enables continuous learning and

adaptation by linking observation, analysis, decision-making, and action. As a result, it is widely used to enhance organizational agility and strategic decision-making in rapidly changing business environments.

2.3 PDCA Cycle

The Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle is a four-stage management approach used for continuous improvement and effective process control within organizations (Lauenroth, 2025). It provides a structured method for problem-solving and enhancing organizational performance. The cycle begins with the “Plan” stage, where organizations identify problems, set objectives, and develop strategies to achieve desired outcomes. This stage involves analyzing internal and external factors, defining stakeholder needs, and establishing a clear action plan. The “Do” stage follows, where planned activities are implemented, and data are collected to evaluate performance. This phase translates strategic plans into practical actions while monitoring progress. The “Check” stage focuses on evaluating the results by analyzing collected data to determine whether objectives have been achieved. It helps identify gaps, inefficiencies, and areas for improvement. Finally, the “Act” stage involves taking corrective actions, refining processes, and standardizing successful practices to ensure continuous improvement. The PDCA cycle supports organizations in managing change, improving quality, and making data-driven decisions, making it a valuable tool for strategic management in dynamic business environments.

2.4 Change Management Plan (Kotter’s 8 Step Change Model)

The change management is important for businesses because it directly determines whether strategic initiatives succeed or fail (Goodwin, 2025). The well-designed strategies remain ineffective without proper change management due to the employees do not understand, accept and implement the change strategies correctly. Change management helps to overcome the business challenges faced during crises. The change strategies need to be structured where the employees clearly understand their roles, business processes, and expectations. A well-managed change process provides effective guidance, training, and support, that allow organization to maintain stability when adopting new operational strategies. The change management strengthens the firms’ ability to adapt in a rapidly evolving business environment. Kotter’s 8-Step Change model is a structured as the roadmap that ensures every step of the change process is accounted for, from the initial assessment to planning to accomplish implementation (Majka, 2024). Kotter’s 8-Step Change model prioritizes leadership, effective communication, and team communication while also addresses the personal and business impacts of change.

III. Methodology and Data Analysis

3.1 Research Design

The current study examines research titled “Workforce Management Challenges in Myanmar SMEs: The Impact of labor migration and economic crisis on strategic decision-making” using quantitative cross-sectional research method. The research targets the SMEs which has minimum one years of operation period and located in major cities. The participants are SMEs’ owners, general managers, HR managers and other senior staff. The primary data are collected using self-reported questionnaire. Before collecting primary data for current study, the researcher sends informed consent letter to recruit the SMEs owners and managers to participate in the study and their information are confidential. The questionnaire is distributed using Google survey form due to difficulties in transportation for face-to-face data collection. The respondents are selected

voluntary, and informed the participants that their data are confidential. Total 126 SMEs owners, and managers participated in this study. The returned data are transformed from Microsoft Excel to statistical software called Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 27) for further data analysis.

3.2 Data Analysis

The descriptive and inferential statistical tests are performed to understand how labor migration and economic crisis impact on strategic decision making in SMEs. The One-way ANOVA test is done to examine which demographic groups face more challenges than others. The regression test is performed to understand impact of labor migration, and economic crisis on strategic decision-making of SMEs in Myanmar.

IV. Findings of the study

4.1 One-way ANOVA tests

Table 1 presents the analysis of the impact of labor migration on different types of SMEs using a One-way ANOVA test. All mean scores are above 4.00, indicating that SMEs across all sectors agree that labor migration significantly affects their workforce. Among the sectors, “others” (education and restaurants) (Mean = 4.667) and “construction” (Mean = 4.650) report the highest mean values, suggesting that these industries experience the strongest impact due to their high dependence on human labor. Similarly, “retail/trade” (Mean = 4.479), “production” (Mean = 4.418), “agriculture” (Mean = 4.417), and “services” (Mean = 4.309) also indicate a high level of impact. However, the ANOVA results show no statistically significant differences in the impact of labor migration across these sectors ($F = 1.462$, $p = 0.207$). This finding suggests that labor migration is a widespread issue affecting all types of SMEs relatively equally. The results indicate that workforce management challenges caused by labor migration are common across industries, regardless of the type of SME.

Table 1: Impact of Labor migration on different types of SMEs

Types of SMEs	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Retail/Trade	42	4.479	0.462					
Services	34	4.309	0.505					
Agriculture	3	4.417	0.191					
Construction	15	4.650	0.367					
Production	29	4.418	0.422					
Others	3	4.667	0.315					
Between groups				1.480	5	0.296	1.462	0.207
Within groups				24.290	120	0.202		
Dependent variable: Labor Migration Impact on workforce								
Compared groups: Types of SMEs								

(Source: Survey data 2026)

Table 2 presents the analysis of the impact of labor migration on SMEs across different locations. Overall, the mean scores for all regions are above 4.00, indicating strong agreement among respondents that labor migration significantly affects SMEs' workforce across the country. Among the locations, SMEs in "other cities" such as Myitkyina, Shwebo, and Taunggyi report the highest mean score (Mean = 4.656), suggesting a greater impact of labor migration in these areas. This is followed by Yangon (Mean = 4.565), Naypyidaw (Mean = 4.553), and Mandalay (Mean = 4.323). These results indicate that SMEs in major urban centers experience slightly lower impacts compared to those in other regions. Furthermore, the ANOVA results reveal statistically significant differences in the impact of labor migration across locations ($F = 3.689$, $p = 0.014$). This suggests that geographic location plays an important role in shaping how labor migration affects SMEs' workforce. The findings highlight that while labor migration impacts all SMEs, its effects vary significantly depending on regional context.

Table 2: Impact of Labor migration on different locations of SMEs

Location of SMEs	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sum squares	of df	Mean square	F	Sig
Yangon	21.000	4.565	0.395					
Mandalay	67.000	4.323	0.507					
Naypyidaw	26.000	4.553	0.347					
Other cities	12.000	4.656	0.227					
Between groups				2.143	3	0.714	3.689	0.014
Within groups				23.627	122	0.194		
Dependent variable: Labor Migration Impact on workforce								
Compared groups: Location of SMEs								

(Source: Survey data 2026)

Table 3 presents the analysis of the impact of the economic crisis on different types of SMEs. Overall, the mean scores for all SME categories are above 4.00, indicating strong agreement among respondents that the economic crisis significantly affects their workforce across industries. Among the sectors, "agriculture" reports the highest mean score (Mean = 4.476), followed by "construction" and "production" (Mean = 4.448 each). These findings suggest that these sectors experience greater workforce challenges due to their high dependence on labor. In comparison, "others" (education and restaurants) (Mean = 4.381), "services" (Mean = 4.227), and "retail/trade" (Mean = 4.194) also report considerable impacts from the economic crisis. However, the ANOVA results indicate no statistically significant differences in the impact of the economic crisis across SME types ($F = 1.539$, $p = 0.183$). The findings suggest that the economic crisis is a widespread issue affecting SMEs similarly across all industries, regardless of sector type.

Table 3: Impact of Economic crisis on different type of SMEs

Types of SMEs	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Retail/Trade	42.000	4.194	0.565	0.087				
Services	34.000	4.227	0.511	0.088				
Agriculture	3.000	4.476	0.165	0.095				
Construction	15.000	4.448	0.411	0.106				
Production	29.000	4.448	0.280	0.052				
Others	3.000	4.381	0.577	0.333				
Between groups				1.731	5	0.346	1.539	0.183
Within groups				26.988	120	0.225		
Dependent variable: Economic Crisis Impact on workforce								
Compared groups: Types of SMEs								

(Source: Survey data 2026)

Table 4 presents the analysis of the impact of the economic crisis on SMEs across different locations. All mean values exceed 4.00, indicating strong agreement among respondents that the economic crisis significantly affects SMEs' workforce across all regions. Among the locations, Naypyidaw reports the highest mean score (Mean = 4.533), followed by "other cities" such as Myitkyina, Shwebo, and Taunggyi (Mean = 4.500), and Yangon (Mean = 4.320). These results suggest that SMEs in these areas experience a relatively stronger impact of the economic crisis on their workforce. Meanwhile, SMEs in Mandalay (Mean = 4.173) also report notable workforce challenges, although to a comparatively lower extent. Furthermore, the ANOVA results indicate statistically significant differences in the impact of the economic crisis across locations ($F = 4.715$, $p = 0.004$). This finding suggests that geographic location plays a critical role in determining the severity of the economic crisis on SMEs' workforce. The results highlight that while the economic crisis affects all SMEs, its impact varies significantly depending on regional context.

Table 4: Impact of Economic crisis on different location of SMEs

Location of SMEs	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Yangon	21.000	4.320	0.435					
Mandalay	67.000	4.173	0.528					
Naypyidaw	26.000	4.533	0.330					
Other cities	12.000	4.500	0.269					

Between groups				2.984	3	0.995	4.715	0.004
Within groups				25.735	122	0.211		
Dependent variable: Economic Crisis Impact on workforce								
Compared groups: Location of SMEs								

(Source: Survey data 2026)

Linear Regression Analysis

The regression results indicate that the model has strong explanatory power and statistical significance. R value (0.686) demonstrates a strong positive relationship between the independent variables and strategic decision-making, while the R² value (0.470) suggests that approximately 47% of the variation in strategic decision-making is explained by the impact of labor migration and the economic crisis on workforce challenges in SMEs. The adjusted R² (0.462) further confirms the model's reliability. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson value (2.114) indicates no serious autocorrelation issues, and the absence of multicollinearity is confirmed by acceptable VIF (1.141) and tolerance (0.876) values. The model is statistically significant (F = 54.643, p < 0.001). Based on the unstandardized coefficients, both independent variables have a positive and statistically significant impact on strategic decision-making (p < 0.001). Labor migration has a significant positive effect (B = 0.268), while the economic crisis shows a stronger impact (B = 0.448). These findings indicate that both labor migration and economic instability are key drivers of SMEs' strategic decision-making, with the economic crisis emerging as the more influential factor in shaping workforce management strategies.

Table 5: Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.209	0.309		3.911	0.000	0.597	1.821		
	Labor Migration Impact on workforce	0.268	0.063	0.296	4.225	0.000	0.142	0.393	0.876	1.141
	Economic Crisis Impact on workforce	0.448	0.060	0.523	7.465	0.000	0.329	0.567	0.876	1.141
R		0.686								
R square		0.470478475								

Adjusted Square	R	0.462
Durbin-Watson		2.114
F		54.643
Sig.		<0.001
a. Dependent Variable: Strategic Decision-making for workforce management		
b. Predictors: (Constant), Economic Crisis Impact on workforce, Labor Migration Impact on workforce		

(Source: Survey data 2026)

Coping strategies for workforce shortages

Figure 1 illustrates the coping strategies adopted by SMEs in response to workforce challenges caused by labor migration and the economic crisis. The findings show that SMEs employ a variety of approaches, including increasing wages and benefits, hiring inexperienced workers, providing training programs, utilizing contract or temporary staff, adopting automation or digital tools, and outsourcing. Among these strategies, increasing wages and benefits is the most widely adopted (reported by 118 respondents), indicating that SMEs prioritize employee retention by offering financial incentives. The second most common strategy is providing training programs (69 respondents), followed by the use of contract or temporary workers (60 respondents) and hiring inexperienced workers (55 respondents). These approaches reflect efforts to address labor shortages and maintain workforce capacity. Additionally, 35 respondents report using automation or digital tools to mitigate labor shortages, although access to advanced technology remains limited. A smaller number of SMEs rely on outsourcing (7 respondents), while only one respondent indicates no significant changes in response to workforce challenges. The results suggest that SMEs adopt a combination of financial incentives, flexible labor practices, and skill development strategies to cope with workforce challenges.

Figure 1: Coping strategies for workforce shortages
(Source: survey data 2026)

V. Discussion

The findings provide crucial managerial implications for SMEs in improving workforce management strategies under challenging conditions. The SMEs' owners, managers, and leaders aware to prioritize employee retention strategies due to labor migration and economic crisis affect directly on workforce management. Lack of skillful workers, offering competitive wages, and providing more training programs for inexperienced workers can increase operational costs, and reduce productivity. Investing in training and development programs can improve workers skills and motivation that require to promote their performance. Moreover, SMEs need to use flexible workforce strategies such as hiring contract or temporary workers to response labor shortage. Recruitment strategies are important to attract suitable candidates through various recruitment channels such as partnerships with training institutions, online platforms and local communities. SMEs need to develop strategies to solve workforce management challenges due to labor migration and economic crisis, and also need to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of implemented strategies align with business goals.

VI. Recommendations for SMEs to adapt workforce management challenges

- 1) **Strengthen Employee Retention Strategies:** SMEs should increase wages and benefits to retain existing employees and remain competitive in the labor market. Financial incentives can reduce turnover and improve workforce stability.
- 2) **Invest in Training and Skill Development:** Providing regular training programs is essential to enhance the skills of both new and existing employees. This helps compensate for the shortage of skilled labor caused by migration.
- 3) **Adopt Flexible Workforce Practices:** SMEs should utilize contract or temporary workers to manage short-term labor shortages and maintain operational continuity during uncertain periods.
- 4) **Improve Recruitment Strategies:** Businesses should adapt recruitment approaches by hiring inexperienced workers and developing them through structured training and mentorship programs.
- 5) **Leverage Technology and Automation:** SMEs are encouraged to adopt digital tools, HR management systems, and automation to improve efficiency and reduce dependence on manual labor.
- 6) **Implement Phased Workforce Planning**
 - Short-term (0–6 months): Focus on immediate actions such as wage increases, temporary hiring, and basic training.
 - Medium-term (6–18 months): Develop structured training systems, improve recruitment, and adopt flexible work arrangements.
 - Long-term (18+ months): Establish sustainable workforce planning and institutionalize HR practices.
- 7) **Enhance Financial Planning and Resource Allocation:** SMEs should carefully allocate budgets for salaries, training, and technology investments while controlling unnecessary costs to maintain financial sustainability.
- 8) **Monitor and Evaluate Strategy Effectiveness:** Regularly assess performance using indicators such as employee retention, productivity, and business growth to ensure continuous improvement.

VII. Conclusion

This study examines the impact of labor migration and economic crisis on workforce management and strategic decision-making in SMEs. The findings reveal that SMEs face major challenges, including shortages of skilled workers, recruitment difficulties, high employee turnover, and rising wage expectations. Economic instability further intensifies these issues by increasing financial pressure, complicating workforce planning, and reducing productivity. Labor migration and the economic crisis are identified as key drivers of workforce challenges across all SME sectors and locations. In response, SMEs adopt coping strategies such as increasing wages, providing training, hiring temporary or inexperienced workers, and using outsourcing. To enhance long-term resilience, SMEs should adopt structured frameworks such as the Cynefin Framework, OODA loop, PDCA cycle, and Kotter's change model. Additionally, collaboration with government and other stakeholders is essential to develop sustainable workforce management strategies and improve competitiveness.

VIII. References

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